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Strategic Roadmap for Advancing Ireland's Open Repository Landscape:

A Brief for Leaders

Authors: Dr Christopher Loughnane, Dr Cillian Joy

<https://www.universityofgalway.ie/openrepositories>

Open Repository Role

In today's global research landscape, Ireland's leadership in open research is critical to maintaining its competitive edge. Achieving the national strategy of 100% open access requires a viable, nationally coordinated **Green OA** alternative to counteract the financial pressures of the current academic publishing model, which has inequitable APCs and unsustainable big-deal subscriptions.

Leaders have a real opportunity to take **swift, coordinated action** to **align open repository infrastructure** with international standards alongside **focused investment** and **strategic alignment** across institutions.

The NORF OA Repositories project has identified key areas of concern that require immediate action to safeguard and enhance institutional repositories nationally.

This briefing outlines **recommended actions** for leaders that will enhance the infrastructure, visibility, and sustainability of open scholarly communication in Ireland. This is underpinned by a well-resourced open repository community backed by leaders, policymakers, and a collective of related national initiatives driven by the National Action Plan for Open Research.

Also included are details about the launch of Open Repositories Ireland, a new membership group for repository staff.

ORI
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Recommended Actions

Challenge	Action
Visibility and Outreach	Align repository efforts with institutional strategies, enhance visibility through targeted outreach and collaboration.
Metadata Quality and Compliance	Encourage repository staff to adopt consistent metadata standards, work with Open Repositories Ireland, and provide staff training and support.
Resources	Support local staffing and advocate for national funding in technical infrastructure and training.

Why Open Repositories?

- Provide free and **open access to research**
- Manage and **preserve** your institution's valuable research outputs
- Participate as a node in a growing **non-commercial alternative** (Diamond and Green) to the commercial publishing system.

Introducing Open Repositories Ireland (ORI)

ORI is a new membership organisation dedicated to advancing open research practices and repository services across Ireland. It provides a collaborative platform for open repository managers and practitioners to share knowledge, develop best practices, and advocate for open research within the Irish research community, supported by their institutional research ecosystems.

ORI focuses on promoting, supporting, and developing open repositories through networking, training, and advocacy. By joining ORI, institutions will contribute to shaping the future of **Green open research** in Ireland and achieving the goal of 100% open access by 2030.

For further information visit:

<https://www.universityofgalway.ie/openrepositories>

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Future Outlook

The roadmap envisions a future where **Ireland emerges as a global leader in open scholarly communication**. By 2030, the aim is to have a robust, sustainable, and inclusive open repository ecosystem that leverages innovative technologies and collaborative partnerships to drive Irish open research.

Achieving this goal requires leaders to **act now** to support their open research repositories.

Key milestones include:

- Strengthening the repository network through investment
- Enhancing metadata quality, and
- Promoting open mandates, particularly focusing on **Green OA** routes as critical to achieving 100% open access by 2030.

Read the full **Strategic Roadmap**:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810233>

